

PREVALENCE AND ASSOCIATED FACTORS OF SELF-MEDICATION
AMONG MEDICAL AND NON-MEDICAL STUDENTS IN CHARSAJDA

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Keywords

Self-medication, medical students, non-medical students, antibiotic misuse, and 'Pakistan

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Abstract

Background: Self-medication—the use of medicines without professional consultation—is a common global phenomenon, especially in developing countries where drugs are easily accessible. Although it may seem convenient and cost-effective, self-medication poses significant risks such as incorrect drug use, delayed diagnosis, and antimicrobial resistance. University students, particularly those in medical and non-medical fields, are among the groups most likely to engage in this practice due to their knowledge, accessibility to medicines, and busy schedules.

Aim: This study aimed to assess the prevalence and associated factors of self-medication among medical and non-medical students in Charsajda.

Methodology: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted among 60 undergraduate students from Bacha Khan University, Charsajda, using a stratified random sampling technique to ensure equal representation of both groups. Data were collected through a structured self-administered questionnaire and analyzed using SPSS version 26. Descriptive and inferential statistics were applied to identify patterns and associations between variables.

Results: The findings revealed that 71.7% of students used self-medication as their first line of treatment. Most respondents (90%) checked expiry dates before using medicines, and 61.7% recognized that overuse could lead to drug resistance. However, 45% considered self-medication a time-saving practice, and 50% viewed it as economical. Common motivations included convenience, affordability, and limited access to healthcare facilities. Despite general awareness of risks, some students underestimated potential dangers such as substance misuse, incorrect drug use, and delayed diagnosis.

Conclusion: Self-medication is highly prevalent among students in Charsajda, influenced by accessibility, cost concerns, and perceived minor illness. While many students demonstrate responsible behavior, gaps remain in understanding the long-term risks. Educational programs and stricter awareness campaigns are recommended to promote safe medication practices and reduce the potential harm

of self-medication.

Keywords:

Self-medication, medical students, non-medical students, antibiotic misuse, Pakistan

INTRODUCTION

Self-medication has been defined as the use of medication for self-treatment without consulting a physician for diagnosis, prescription, or surveillance of treatment. It involves obtaining medication without prescription and taking medicines on advice from unauthenticated websites and vlogs. (World health organization) 2019.

Self-medication is common in both developed and developing countries but higher in developing countries, due to wider increase of drug availability without prescription. (Pandya et al., 2013). Self-medication increases the possibility of drug abuse and drug dependency. It also masks the signs and symptoms of underlying diseases, hence complicating the problem, creating drug resistance, and delaying diagnosis. (Mehmood et al., 2020). Self-medication has been reported to be on the rise globally. The World Health Organization (WHO) emphasized that self-medication must be correctly taught and controlled in other to avoid drug related issues such as antimicrobial resistance which is now a current problem worldwide particularly in developing countries where antibiotics are often available without a prescription. According to William Osler, a great feature, which distinguishes man from animals, is the desire to take medicine. as cited in Islam & Hossain, 2019).Self-medication involves the use of medicinal products by the individuals to treat self-recognized disorders or symptoms, or the intermittent or continuous use of a medication prescribed by a physician for chronic or recurring diseases or symptoms. Self-medication involves acquiring medicines without a prescription, resubmitting old prescriptions to purchase medicines, sharing medicines with relatives or members of one's social circle or using leftover medicines stored at home. (Pandya et al., 2013). Self-medication thus forms an integral part of self-care, which can be defined as the primary public health resource in the health care system. It includes self-medication, non-drug self-treatment, social support in illness, and first aid in everyday life. The youth are highly influenced by the

media and the internet, which promote self-medication behavior. The increased advertising of pharmaceuticals possesses a larger threat of self-medication to the younger population in general. This raises concerns of incorrect self-diagnosis, drug interaction, and use of drugs other than for the original indication (Mehmood et al.,2020).The increase in the quantities and varieties of pharmaceuticals worldwide eases the accessibility of medicine by consumers, thereby giving options for its misuse.(WHO, 2019).

In most developing countries such as Ethiopia, many drugs are dispensed over the counter, and the majority of the medical conditions, nearly 60 percent of population, are treated through self-medication at optional and cheaper costs. (East Mediterranean Health Journal [EMHJ], 2020).However, there is a clear difference between the practices of self-medication with over the-counter drugs and the way of purchasing and using prescription only medicines without a doctor's order. This means that the rule of over-the-counter medicines is violated in developing countries, particularly in our setup since many prescription-only drugs are purchased and used at OTC corners. This is potentially a dangerous kind of self-prescription, and such type of practice is common in many developing countries such as Ethiopia. This facilitates the emergence of antimicrobial resistance. (EMHJ, 2020).Hence, the national drug regulatory authority needs to evaluate, approve, and list drugs that are safe for self-medication. Previous studies have shown that medical knowledge is one of the factors that could have an impact on self-medication practice among college students. With the assumption difference in the level of preexisting medical knowledge, (Islam & Hossain, 2019).several studies have compared self-medication between medical and nonmedical students. However, it is difficult to establish a clear relationship between the role of medical education and self-medication practice among students because of divergent results of the studies. In addition, the increasing availability of medicinal

products with diversity in its quantities and variety could motivate people to practice self-medication. Therefore, this study was conducted to assess the prevalence of self-medication practices and its associated factors among medical and non-medical students.

Background

Self-medication refers to the use of drugs by individuals to treat self-diagnosed conditions without consulting a qualified health professional (World Health Organization [WHO], 2021). It includes acquiring medicines without prescription, reusing old prescriptions, or using leftover medications at home. This practice is increasingly common worldwide but is more prevalent in developing countries where medications are often sold without prescription (Esan et al., 2018).

Self-medication poses major public health risks such as drug resistance, adverse drug reactions, and masking of serious diseases (Kumar et al., 2013). The misuse of antibiotics, in particular, contributes to the global rise of antimicrobial resistance. Among university students, factors such as easy drug accessibility, peer influence, online health information, and limited time to visit health facilities encourage self-medication (S. Khalid et al., 2020). In Pakistan and other developing nations, both medical and non-medical students frequently practice self-the limited body of literature from Pakistan on the behavioral and educational differences affecting self-medication between medical and non-medical students. Ultimately, understanding these differences can guide national strategies to prevent drug misuse and antimicrobial resistance.

Research question

What is the prevalence of self-medication and the associated influencing factors among medical and non-medical university students in Charsadda?

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

- 1- To assess the prevalence of self-medication practices among medical and non-medical students.
- 2- To assess the knowledge about factors associated with self-medication practices.

medication. While medical students may rely on their pharmacological knowledge, non-medical students often depend on advice from friends or online sources. These behavioral differences highlight the need to assess and compare the prevalence and associated factors of self-medication across both groups to inform preventive strategies.

Problem statement

Despite awareness of the risks, self-medication remains widespread among students in Pakistan. Easy access to pharmaceuticals, lack of regulatory enforcement, and misconceptions about drug safety have normalized this behavior. However, little is known about the prevalence and factors influencing self-medication among medical and non-medical students in Charsadda. Without such data, it is difficult to design targeted interventions to reduce unsafe self-medication practices and promote rational drug use.

Significance of study

This study is significant because it provides local evidence on the extent and patterns of self-medication among university students in Charsadda. The findings will help educators, policymakers, and health professionals develop awareness programs that discourage irrational drug use. It also contributes to

Summary

The introduction defines self-medication as the use of medicines by individuals to treat self-diagnosed illnesses without consulting qualified health professionals. It highlights that this practice, while common globally, is more prevalent in developing countries like Pakistan due to easy access to drugs, weak regulation, and growing trust in online medical information. The chapter emphasizes that self-medication poses major risks such as antimicrobial resistance, adverse drug reactions, and delayed diagnosis. It notes that university students, particularly medical and non-medical students, are among the most frequent practitioners because of time constraints, prior knowledge, and confidence in self-care. However, limited research exists on this behavior in Charsadda, making it essential to explore the prevalence and factors associated with self-medication among students in this area. The chapter concludes by

presenting the research question, which focuses on assessing the prevalence and influencing factors of self-medication among medical and non-medical students, and outlines objectives aimed at

understanding knowledge levels, behaviors, and preventive need

SEARCH STRATEGY AND CRITERIA

A comprehensive literature search was conducted using databases including Pub Med, Google Scholar, Research Gate, and Science Direct.

Keywords

Self-medication, medical students, non-medical students, antibiotic misuse, and 'Pakistan.

Inclusion criteria

Included peer-reviewed studies published between 2020 and 2024, studies involving university students, and articles available in English.

Exclusion criteria

Included studies before 2020, grey literature, and articles without full text. Twelve studies met the inclusion criteria and were reviewed for this section.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Northwest Ethiopia from March 25 to May 15, 2018. A comparative sample of 213 medical and 212 nonmedical students were enrolled in the study. Data were collected by physically visiting the students in their campuses, using a semi-structured questionnaire. Of the participants with a history of medication use in the past 12 months, 64.5% practiced self-medication. The prevalence of self-medication was 59.7% among medical students and 69.0% among nonmedical students. "Knowing the treatment of the disease" was the most frequent reason behind self-medication. Analgesics/antipyretics were the most common categories of medications used, whereas headache was the predominant ailment for which the medications were used. In conclusion, self-medication is common in students. Nonmedical students were more likely to have practiced self-medication as compared to medical students. Deborah Tolulope Esan, Ayodeji Akinwande Fasoro, Opeoluwa Esther Odesanya, Theophilus Olaide Esan, Elizabeth Funmilayo Ojo and Charles Oluwafemi Faeji conducted research on the practice of self-medication among undergraduate students of a private university in Nigeria. The study employed a descriptive cross-sectional design. A pretested questionnaire was self-administered to 384 undergraduate students of the university. Data were analyzed and summarized using descriptive and inferential statistics such as chi-squared and Fisher's exact tests. Overall, 297 (81.8%) undergraduate students practiced self-medication. About 71% of the students had used analgesic, antibiotics (10.5%), and ant malarial drugs (33%) without prescription within one month prior to the survey. The most commonly used drug for self-medication was paracetamol (75.1%). Furthermore, self-medication was found to be significantly associated with age, gender, college, and year of study, some of the reasons why undergraduate students practiced self-medication were because of the unfriendly attitude of health care workers (27.7%), lack of time to go to school clinic (26.7%), school clinic is too far from hostel (15.3%), and drugs prescribed in the school clinic do not improve health condition (15.3%). Conclusion. Majority of the students attributed the practice of self-medication to unfriendly attitude of health care workers in the university clinic (20). Nithin Kumar,

Tanuj Kanchan, Bhaskaran Unnikrishnan, T. Rekha, Prasanna Mithra, Vaman Kulkarni, Mohan Kumar Papanna, Ramesh Holla and Surabhi Uppal conducted research to access the prevalence of self-medication among the medical students in South India. The data was analyzed using SPSS version 11.5. 440 students were included in the study. The prevalence of self-medication was 78.6%. A larger number of females were self-medicating (81.2%) than males (75.3%). The majority of the students self-medicated because of the illness being too trivial for consultation (70.5%). Antipyretics were most commonly self-medicated by the participants (74.8%). Only 47% of the participants opined that self-medication was a part of self-care and it needs to be encouraged. 39.3% of the participants perceived that the supply of medicine without prescription by the pharmacist could prevent the growing trend of self-medication. Easy availability and accessibility to health care facilities remains the cornerstone for reducing the practice of self-medication (21). S Khalid, Q Ali, MM Hafeez and A Malik from Institute of Molecular Biology & Biotechnology, University of Lahore, Pakistan conducted research to assess the wrong practice of self-medication in public sector universities of Southern Punjab. The current study also compares the self-medication practices in various departments of universities. A validated questionnaire was used to collect data. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the data and inferential statistics (chi-square test). The study was included data from 900 students including both males and females from various departments. Among 900 students, 450 students of medical while 450 were non-medical students. Frequency of self-medication was found to 57 %. The antibiotics more frequently use for self-medication were Augmentin (37 %), Amoxicillin (23 %). Fever and cough were the most frequent indication for the use of self-medicated antibiotics. Because of their sufficient knowledge of pharmacology, most students were self-medicated (40%). Academic knowledge is the principal source of antibiotic information (60%). Just (39%) of the students thought that self-medication is part of the self-core, 31% of the students perceived that the availability of non-prescription drugs could prevent the growing trend of self-medication with antibiotics.

30% of students perceived that antibiotics were aware of the harms of self-medication or informed about them. Based on this study, it can be concluded that a high proportion of medical students and non-medical students use antibiotics without medical prescription and such practices are more common in the general public sector.

Summary

The literature review presents evidence from multiple studies conducted in Ethiopia, Nigeria, India, Saudi Arabia, Pakistan, and Bangladesh. These studies consistently show that self-medication is highly prevalent among university students, with rates ranging from 57% to 81%. The most commonly used drugs include analgesics, antipyretics, and antibiotics, often taken to treat headaches, fever, or minor illnesses.

The review identifies several factors influencing self-medication, including academic pressure, prior experience with certain drugs, easy pharmacy access, peer influence, and confidence in medical knowledge (especially among medical students). The search

strategy for this review used databases such as Pub Med, Google Scholar, and Research Gate, focusing on English-language articles published between 2020 and 2024.

Overall, the reviewed studies reveal that non-medical students are slightly more prone to self-medication than medical students are. The review concludes that while self-medication remains a convenient short-term solution for minor health problems, it poses serious long-term risks. The chapter emphasizes the need for education programs and stricter regulation to promote safe and rational drug use among university students.

Chapter 03METHODOLO

Introduction

This chapter explain the research methodology it describe the research design ,approach, study setting, population, sampling technique, data collection tool, procedure, and analysis method, the purpose of this chapter is to provide a clear understanding of how the study was conducted.

Approach	Quantitative
Study design	Descriptive cross-sectional survey
Study area	Charsadda university bacha khan
Study population	Undergraduate medical and non medical students
Sampling technique	stratified random sampling technique
Sample size	60
Inclusion criteria	The study included undergraduate medical and non medical students
Exclusion criteria	Students who decline participation. postgraduate students
Data collection Toll	Questionnaires,
Data collection process	Institute principal approval, approach to students, informed consent, questionnaire distribution.

Data analysis	SPSS 26 version software
Duration	3 months
Validity and Reliability	Pilot testing,
Ethical consideration	Approval will be obtained from the Ethical Review Committee. Informed consent will be taken. Confidentiality will be maintained.

Research Design

This study employs a descriptive cross-sectional research design to assess the prevalence and associated factors of self-medication among medical and non-medical university students in Charsadda. A cross-sectional design is suitable because it allows the researcher to collect data from a population at a single point in time, making it effective for estimating prevalence and identifying associated factors (Setia, 2016).

Study Setting

The study will be conducted in selected university Bacha Khan located in Charsadda, Pakistan,

Study Population

The study population will include undergraduate medical and non-medical students currently enrolled in Bacha Khan University in Charsadda.

Sample size and sampling technique.

60 students will be selected using a stratified random sampling technique, ensuring equal representation from medical and non-medical disciplines. Stratification will reduce selection bias and allow

Validity and reliability

A pilot test will be conducted with 10 students to ensure clarity, reliability, and validity before the main study.

Data Collection Procedure

Data Analysis

Data will be entered and analyzed using IBM SPSS version 26.0.

comparison between both groups (Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

Inclusion Criteria

Undergraduate medical and non-medical students enrolled in university in Charsadda.

Students who give informed consent to participate. Those present during the data collection period.

Exclusion Criteria

Students who decline participation.

Postgraduate students

Data Collection Tool

A structured self-administered questionnaire the questionnaire will have three sections:

1. Demographic data (name, age, gender, department, academic level, and family income).
2. Self-medication practices (frequency, types of drugs used, and sources of drugs).
3. Factors associated with self-medication (knowledge, accessibility, peer influence, and attitudes)

Duration.

The total duration of the study will be two months, including preparation, data collection, and analysis,

Permission will be obtained from university authorities. The questionnaires will be distributed to participants during regular class hours and collected after completion. The purpose of the study will be explained, and confidentiality will be maintained throughout the process. Descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage, mean, mode median and standard deviation) will be used to describe prevalence.

Inferential statistics, such as the Chi-square test, will assess associations between demographic variables and self-medication practices (Field, 2018).

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval will be obtained from the Ethical Review Committee of the concerned university. Informed consent will be taken from participants. Participation will be voluntary, and confidentiality and anonymity will be assured.

Chapter 04 RESULTS

```
GETDATA SET ACTIVATE DataSet1.
FREQUENCIES VARIABLES=q1q2q3q4
q5q6q7q8q9q10q11q12q13q14
/STATISTICS=STD DEV MINIMUM MAXIMUM
MEAN MEDIAN MODE
/BAR CHART FREQ
/ORDER=ANALYSIS.
Frequencies
[DataSet1]C:\Users\ss\Desktop\aaamirbacha.sav
Statistics
```

		age	gender	department	academiclevel	familyincome	do you use self medicationasa first form of treatment?
N	Valid	60	60	60	60	60	60
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		21.47					1.2833
Median		21.00					1.0000
Mode							45447
Std.Deviation		21					
Minimum		1.214					

Statistics

		overuseof some drug can result in drug resistance?	In case of side effect physicians help must be sought?	can self medication save time?	is self medication economical?	Is self medication enough to treat mild illness?
N	Valid	60	60	60	60	60
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		1.5333	1.5333	1.7500	1.7333	1.5667
Median		1.0000	1.0000	2.0000	1.5000	1.0000
Mode		1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Std.Deviation						
Minimum						

		do you check for the expiry date of the medication you use?	can self-medication lead to risk of incorrect medicine?	can self-medication delay the diagnose?	can self-medication lead to dangerous drug response?	can self-medication lead to substance abuse?
N	Valid	60	60	60	60	60
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		1.1000	1.6500	1.7167	1.6167	1.8333
Median		1.0000	1.0000	2.0000	1.0000	2.0000
Mode		1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Std.Deviation		.30253	.77733	.76117	.71525	.80605
Minimum		1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Maximum		2.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00

Statistics

Statistics

		can self-medication no hospital nearby minimize physical visits? lead to self-medication?	can self-medication give confidence?
N	Valid	60	60
	Missing	0	0
Mean		1.7167	1.7333
Median		1.0000	1.5000
Mode		1.00	1.00
St. Deviation		.86537	.82064
Minimum		1.00	1.00
Maximum		3.00	3.00

Frequency Table

age	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	19	3.3	3.3	3.3
	20	20.0	20.0	23.3
	21	30.0	30.0	53.3

	22	14	23.3	23.3	76.7
	23	12	20.0	20.0	96.7
	24	2	3.3	3.3	100.0
	Total	60	100.0	100.0	

gender

Frequency		Percent	Valid Percent	umulative Percent
Valid	female	25	41.7	41.7
	male	35	58.3	100.0
	Total	60	100.0	100.0

department

Frequency		Percent	Valid Percent	umulative Percent
Valid	botony	6	10.0	10.0
	computer	6	10.0	20.0
	ecnomic	6	10.0	30.0
	english	6	10.0	40.0
	pharmD	30	50.0	90.0
	zoology	6	10.0	100.0
	Total	60	100.0	100.0

academic level

Frequency		Percent	Valid Percent	umulative Percent
Valid	bs	60	100.0	100.0

family income

Frequency		Percent	Valid Percent	umulative Percent
Valid	100000	2	3.3	3.3
	110000	1	1.7	5.0
	150000	2	3.3	8.3
	23000	1	1.7	10.0

30000	1	1.7	1.7	11.7
33000	1	1.7	1.7	13.3
35000	6	10.0	10.0	23.3
37000	1	1.7	1.7	25.0
40000	2	3.3	3.3	28.3
41000	3	5.0	5.0	33.3
45000	5	8.3	8.3	41.7
50000	9	15.0	15.0	56.7
51000	1	1.7	1.7	58.3
55000	4	6.7	6.7	65.0
56000	1	1.7	1.7	66.7
60000	5	8.3	8.3	75.0
67000	1	1.7	1.7	76.7
70000	2	3.3	3.3	80.0
75000	2	3.3	3.3	83.3

family income

Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
77000	1	1.7	85.0
79000	1	1.7	86.7
80000	2	3.3	90.0
85000	2	3.3	93.3
90000	4	6.7	100.0
Total	60	100.0	

Do you use self-medication as a first form of treatment?

Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid yes	43	71.7	71.7
no	17	28.3	100.0
Total	60	100.0	

do you check for the expiry date of the medication you use?

Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid yes	54	90.0	90.0

no	6	10.0	10.0	100.0
Total	60	100.0	100.0	

Can self-medication lead to risk of incorrect medicine?

Frequency		Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	agree	32	53.3	53.3
	neutral	17	28.3	81.7
	disagree	11	18.3	100.0
	Total	60	100.0	100.0

Can self-medication delay the diagnose?

Frequency		Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	agree	28	46.7	46.7
	neutral	21	35.0	81.7
	disagree	11	18.3	100.0
	Total	60	100.0	100.0

Can self-medication lead to dangerous drugs response?

Frequency		Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	agree	31	51.7	51.7
	neutral	21	35.0	86.7
	disagree	8	13.3	100.0
	Total	60	100.0	100.0

Can self-medication lead to substance abuse?

Frequency		Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	agree	25	41.7	41.7
	neutral	20	33.3	75.0
	disagree	15	25.0	100.0
	Total	60	100.0	100.0

Over use of some drug can result in drug resistance?

Frequency		Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
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Valid	agree	37	61.7	61.7	61.7
	neutral	14	23.3	23.3	85.0
	disagree	9	15.0	15.0	100.0
	Total	60	100.0	100.0	

In case of side effect physicians help must be sought?

Frequency		Percent	Valid Percent	umulative Percent	
Valid	agree	36	60.0	60.0	60.0
	neutral	16	26.7	26.7	86.7
	disagree	8	13.3	13.3	100.0
	Total	60	100.0	100.0	

Can self-medication save time?

Frequency		Percent	Valid Percent	umulative Percent	
Valid	agree	27	45.0	45.0	45.0
	neutral	21	35.0	35.0	80.0
	disagree	12	20.0	20.0	100.0
	Total	60	100.0	100.0	

Is self-medication economical?

Frequency		Percent	Valid Percent	umulative Percent	
Valid	agree	30	50.0	50.0	50.0
	neutral	16	26.7	26.7	76.7
	disagree	14	23.3	23.3	100.0
	Total	60	100.0	100.0	

Is self-medication enough to treat mild illness?

Frequency		Percent	Valid Percent	umulative Percent	
Valid	agree	32	53.3	53.3	53.3
	neutral	22	36.7	36.7	90.0
	disagree	6	10.0	10.0	100.0
	Total	60	100.0	100.0	

Can self-medication minimize physical visits?

Frequency			Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	agree	33	55.0	55.0	55.0
	neutral	11	18.3	18.3	73.3
	disagree	16	26.7	26.7	100.0
	Total	60	100.0	100.0	

No hospital nearby can lead to self-medication?

Frequency			Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	agree	26	43.3	43.3	43.3
	neutral	16	26.7	26.7	70.0
	disagree	18	30.0	30.0	100.0
	Total	60	100.0	100.0	

Can self-medication give confidence?

Frequency			Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	agree	30	50.0	50.0	50.0
	neutral	16	26.7	26.7	76.7
	disagree	14	23.3	23.3	100.0
	Total	60	100.0	100.0	

Bar Chartage

zoology

Botony computer ecnomic English pharmD
department

academic level

60

50

40

30

20

10

0

Frequenc

bs

academic level

Family income

Family income

Do you use self-medication as a first form of treatment?

40

30

Frequenc

20

10

0

yes

no

Do you use self-medication as a first form of treatment?

Most students (71.7%) said they take medicine on their own when they feel sick, instead of going to a doctor. This is probably because it's easy to get medicine without a prescription and they want to save time. Other studies show similar habits among university students, where small health problems are treated at home. But this can be risky, as they might use the wrong medicine or not know what the real problem is. That's why it's important to teach students how to use medicine safely.

Do you check for the expiry date of the medication you use?

50

40

30

20

10

0

Frequency

yes

no

Do you check for the expiry date of the medication you use?

what they've learned seriously and using it in real life to protect themselves.

Almost all the students (90%) said they make sure to check the expiry date before taking any medicine. This shows they're being smart and careful about their health. They seem to understand that using expired medicine can be dangerous or less effective. This kind of awareness likely comes from what they've learned in nursing or health-related classes, where they're taught to pay attention to small but important details like drug safety. It's a good sign that they're taking

Can self-medication lead to risk of incorrect medicine?

30

Freuquenc

20

10

0

Agree

neutral

disagree

Can self-medication lead to risk of incorrect medicine?

More than half of the students (53.3%) said yes, it can, while some (18.3%) said no. This means many students understand that taking medicine without a doctor's advice can lead to mistakes. That's a good thing. But since some students didn't agree or weren't sure, it shows that not everyone sees the risk. So, universities should teach more about which medicines are safe to use and when it's important to get medical help.

Can self-medication delay the diagnose?

agree

Can self-medication delay the diagnose?
Almost half of the students think that taking medicine on their own can make it take longer to find out what's really wrong. This happens because people sometimes try to handle symptoms themselves instead of going to the doctor right away. But waiting too long Can self-medication lead to dangerous drugs response?

can make the problem worse. That's why nursing students should learn and teach others to spot warning signs early and get medical help when needed.

30

Frequenc

20

10

0

agree

neutral

disagree

can self-medication lead to dangerous drugs response?

About half of the students (51.7%) agreed that taking medicine without proper guidance can lead to dangerous side effects. This matches other studies that show people often experience bad reactions or drug interactions when they use medication on their own. It's good that many students are aware of this risk, but they also need more training on how to use medicines safely and watch for any problems.

Can self-medication lead to substance abuse?

Agree neutral
can self-medication lead to substance abuse?
disagree

Around 41.7% of students agreed that self-medicating can lead to substance abuse, while 33.3% were unsure, and 25% disagreed. This mixed response shows that many students recognize the risk, but some

don't fully understand that regularly using medicines like painkillers or sedatives without a doctor's advice can cause addiction. It's important to provide more education to raise awareness about these dangers

Over use of some drug can result in drug resistance?

Over use of some drug can result in drug resistance?
Most students (61.7%) agreed that overusing certain drugs can lead to drug resistance. This shows they understand the serious problem caused by misusing antibiotics. They know that taking antibiotics too often or when not needed can make bacteria stronger and harder to treat. This awareness suggests that public health education is working well among these students.

In case of side effect physicians help must be sought?

agree

in case of side effect physicians help must be sought? Most students (60%) agreed that if they experience side effects from medicine, they should see a doctor. This is a good sign, showing they understand the importance of getting professional help when

problems arise. However, around 40% were unsure or disagreed, which means some still try to handle side effects on their own. This can be dangerous, so more education is needed to encourage safer behavior.

Can self-medication save time?

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20

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Agree neutral disagree

can self-medication save time?

About 45% of students believe that self-medication helps save time. This shows that many choose to treat themselves because it's quicker and more convenient than going to doctor. While this makes sense, it can

also be risky because it might lead to unsafe practices or delay getting right treatment when needed. Is self-medication economical?

is self-medication economical?

About half of the students (50%) think that self-medicating saves money. This shows that financial concerns play a big role in why students choose to treat themselves. But while it might save money upfront, using the wrong medicine can cause bigger

health problems and costs later on. Nurses should work to make healthcare more affordable and easier to access so people don't have to rely on unsafe self-treatment.

Is self-medication enough to treat mild illness?

40

20

10

0

Agree

neutral

disagree

is self-medication enough to treat mild illness?

More than half of the students (53.3%) believe that self-medicating is enough to handle mild illnesses like headaches or colds. While treating minor issues at home can be okay sometimes, relying on this too

much can cause problems like taking the wrong dose or medicine. It's important to be careful and know when to see a healthcare professional.

can self-medication minimize physical visits?

disagree

Around 55% of students believe that self-medicating can cut down the number of doctor visits. This highlights that convenience is a big reason why people treat themselves, especially since the COVID-19

pandemic made going to hospitals more difficult. Still, relying too much on self-treatment might result in missing important medical diagnoses and professional help.

No hospital nearby can lead to self-medication?

0

Agree neutral disagree

no hospital nearby can lead to self-medication?

About 43.3% of students agreed that not having a hospital nearby can lead people to self-medicate, while 30% disagreed. This suggests that when healthcare

facilities are hard to reach, people are more likely to treat themselves. It shows the need to improve access to healthcare and provide better outreach services

Can self-medication give confidence?

10

0

Agree.Neutral.disagree

can self-medication give confidence?

About half of the students (50%) said that self-medication makes them feel more confident. independence and control over their health. While feeling confident about handling minor health problems is good, it's important to also understand when professional help is needed to avoid taking unnecessary risks.

This means that treating themselves gives people a sense

questions, and cross tabulation was also used to examine relationships among the variables.

Finding:

Student responses regarding self-medication practices were examined through descriptive analysis. The result is discussed below question by question to explain the trends and perceptions among respondents.

In the term of question 1st about the use of self-medication as a first form of treatment. A large majority 71.7%of students answered yes, while 28.3% said NO. this shows that most students prefer to take medicines by themselves without seeking advice a doctor when they feel sick the result indicates that students depend highly on self-treatment methods, maybe due to easy access to medicines and belief that minor health issues can be handled independently. Moreover, in the term of

Chapter 05 discussion result on self-medication practices

Introduction

The data was analyzed using SPSS version 26, and first checked for completeness. Descriptive statistics and frequencies were applied to examine the variable including the overall questionnaire. Frequency table and bar chat were used to organize responses for each question in the form of agree, neutral, and disagree levels. This helped in understanding the attitude, opinions, and practices of students regarding self-medication. The overall findings were determined by assessing the responses for all

question 2nd regarding checking the expiry date of the medication before use, a most people 90% of respondents reported that they check expiry date of the medication, while only 10% said they do not. This reflects a positive safety attitude among students who seem aware the expired drugs can be harmful or ineffective this awareness might be due to their education prior knowledge of pharmaceutical safety. In the term of question 3rd, which was about whether self-medication can lead to risk of using wrong medication, more than half 53.3% of the respondents agreed, 28.3% were neutral, while 18.3% disagreed. This means that the majority of students understood that taking medicines without medical advice can be risky. However, the presence of neutral and disagreeing responses show that some students don't fully recognize the possibility of errors in medicine use. Furthermore, in the term of question 4th about whether self-medication can delay the diagnoses of illness, 46.7% of students agreed, 35% were neutral, and 18.3% disagreed. This shows that almost half of the students realize that taking medicine without visiting a doctor might postpone accurate diagnose and treatment. The result show that student have a moderate level of understanding about how self-treatment can sometimes hide real medical condition. Moreover, the data or the question about whether self-medication can lead to dangerous drug responses revealed that 51.7% agreed, 35% were neutral, and 13.3% disagreed. This shows that many students are aware that self-medication can have harmful side effects or cause surprise side effect. However, a fair number of neutral respondents indicate that not all students are fully aware of the potential dangers. In the term of question 6th related to whether self-medication can lead substance abuse, 41.7% agreed, 33.3% were neutral, and 25% disagreed. The finding show that while some students recognize the link between self-medication and possible addiction, other remain uncertain or disagreed. This suggests a need for more awareness about the misuse of certain medicines such as painkiller or sedatives. Furthermore, for question 7th which was about the overuse of some drugs leading to drug resistance, a majority 61.7% of students agreed, 23.3% were neutral, and 15% disagreed. The results show that most students make sense of the dangers of

overusing medicines, particularly antibiotics. It also indicates awareness about how to often or done the wrong way use can make drugs less effective over time. In the term of question 8th about whether in case of side effect a physician's help must be sought, 60% agreed, 26.7% were neutral, and 13.3% disagreed. This mean that most students understand importance of consulting a doctor if they go through side effects. Still, the remaining respondents who were neutral or disagreed may prefer managing side impact on them, which would be risky in some cases. Furthermore, in the question 9th concerning whether self-medication helps save time, 45% of respondents agreed, 35% were neutral, and 20% disagreed. This show that many students believe taking medicine by themselves in quicker than visiting a doctor. This attitude reflects easy access as major reason for the practice of self-medication. Moreover, the data for the question 10th regarding whether self-medication is economical revealed that 50% agreed, 26.7% were neutral, and 23.3% disagreed. These finding indicate that financial concern play a significant role in affecting students' choices. Most students believe that self-treatment help then save money by avoiding consultation fees. In the term of question 11th about whether self-medication in enough to treat mild illnesses, 53.3% of respondents agreed, 36.7% were neutral, and 10% disagreed. This result recommended that the majority of students feel trusted friends treating minor ailments like colds, headaches, and flu on their own. However, such confidence may support frequent unsupervised use of medicine. Furthermore, in the question 12th which was about whether self-medication can reduce physical visits to hospitals, 55% of respondents agreed, 18.3% were neutral, and 26.7% disagreed. This implies that students prefer to deal with small health problems by themselves to avoid long waiting times or travel, particularly when they view their illness as mild. Moreover, in the term of question 13th regarding whether the absence of nearby hospitals can lead to self-medication, 43.3% agreed, 26.7% were neutral, and 30% disagreed. This show that limited access to healthcare services can motivate some students to rely on self-medication. However, the varied responses suggest that accessibility is only one of several influencing factors. Lastly in term of question 14th about whether self-

medication gives confidence to individuals, 50% of students agreed, 26.7% were neutral, and 23.3% disagreed. This indicates that many students believe self-medicating help them feel more capable of managing their health issues. While this may show independence, it also reflects a risk of becoming too sure of themselves and ignoring professional advice.

Overall interpretation:

The majority of students practice self-medication and believe it is convenient, economical, and time saving.

However, a significant portion of respondents showed concerns about the risks associated with self-medication, such as incorrect drug use, side effects, and drugs resistance. The data bring attention to that while students demonstrate awareness of safety measure like checking expiry dates and consulting physicians, there are still important missing areas in understanding the dangers of substance misuse and delayed diagnose.

Conclusion:

Overall, the findings point out that self-medication is a common practice among students, supported by factors such as easy access to medicine, financial considerations, and lack of nearby hospitals. Although most students showed awareness about drug safety and side effects, some continue to engage in harmful habits it is therefore recommended that awareness campaigns and educational sessions be organized to encourage proper self-medication practices and to ensure students understand when professional medical help is necessary.